

AFRICA

MOÇAMBIQUE PEMBA!

Let us take a journey to know our wonderful countryside through talking and playing in Portuguese

MUINDI
SEMI DI
SORRIS

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Cover: To raise awareness of the importance of nutrition, we explored the topic of breakfast. In Brazil, breakfast is called 'café da manhã' (literally morning coffee) and in Portugal it is called 'pequeno almoço' (literally small lunch). Interestingly, in Mozambique, they use the expression 'mata-bicho', which literally means 'bug killer'.

So, to have breakfast is 'mata-bicho' which translates as 'to kill the bug'. It comes from the concept that when someone wakes up in the morning feeling hungry, the wriggling feeling in your stomach is the 'bicho' (the bug). So, what better way to 'kill' it (i.e. soothe your hunger) than with piece of bread or something!

"Let us take a journey to know our wonderful countryside through talking and playing in Portuguese"

Multiculturalism, diversity, thoughts, habits, language, and a thousand and one shades of colour make us integrate in multiple and varying circumstances, in which, before we dare to ask about the whys and wherefores, we should give ourselves the pleasure of smiling and listening.

Following the path by public transport from Maputo, one comes to realize the immensity of nature, land, scenery, natural resources and space in Mozambique.

This country does not conceal its enormous and valuable natural wealth which has been exploited over the last decade by international companies. At the same time, it does not hide its population with a huge number of necessities and its fragile education about the environment that must be protected by themselves and also by the state.

Despite the county's social problems, Mozambique is also a land of history, tradition, culture, diversity, friendship, friendly people and traditional music. With respect to music, they love dancing; the movement of their bodies is so important when mixed with African rhythms and songs. They have music in their blood.

Mozambican architecture consists of a few colonial structures such as churches, houses, ports and villages where many Portuguese families lived many years ago before independence. Meanwhile, we can admire some traditional houses, many of which have a small garden where they grow vegetables or fruit to consume or sell.

Today, Pemba, where I spent six weeks, is a city which speaks for itself about the disparities between the wealth and poverty of Mozambican people. In a nutshell, Mozambique is a country with clear contrasts, where we can see many remnants and consequences of being an ex-Portuguese colony.

Uma imagem que deixa perceber essa imensidão de riqueza natural Moçambicana. O mar bem azul, limpo, o sol que não se desliga que não se esquece pelo turista. Temos aqueles meninos pescadores moçambicanos, jogando, gostando de ficar na praia, no sol, esperando o momento preciso para entrar no mar e pescar seus peixinhos de muitas cores, tamanhos e sabores.

This picture shows us Mozambique's huge natural wealth. The Indian Sea, which is very blue and clean, and the Sun which does not turn off cannot be forgotten by tourists. Here, all the children and fishermen are playing and enjoying being in the sun at the beach. They are just waiting for the right time to go fishing in the sea and catch their tiny or huge colourful and tasty fish.

They were carrying heavy bundles on their heads, walking towards the beach.

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A photograph of two young girls sitting together. The girl on the left is wearing a white dress with a red checkered collar and is pointing her right index finger towards the camera. The girl on the right is wearing a yellow top with a large pink ruffled collar and blue patterned shorts. She has small white bows in her hair. They are in a room with yellow and teal walls.

I strongly believe that every child has the right to be a child and to be allowed to develop and be educated in a safe and positive environment.

They need to be encouraged to use their imagination, to dream, to play, to express themselves, to feel their importance in their own community and, most importantly, to smile in an environment free of sexual molestation.

BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Education: The crucial factor for poverty alleviation and development.

Since independence, the Government of the Republic of Mozambique sees education as a fundamental right of every citizen, an instrument for the assertion and integration of the individual in social, economic and political life, an indispensable factor for the continuation of the construction of a society Mozambique and the fight against poverty.

Republic of Mozambique, Ministry of Education.

Characteristics of the municipality of Cabo Delgado

The town of Pemba is the capital of Cabo Delgado Province, with a total population of 138.716 inhabitants, representing 37 % of the population living in urban areas. Of these, 41.8 % are young people under 15 years of age. The city is divided into 10 districts.

The main concerns

- 1) To increase the number of schools and improve the quality of education.
 - 2) To provide health.
 - 3) To ensure the protection of vulnerable children.
 - 4) Children have to be protected from sexual abuse and violence in their environment and in their own school.
 - 5) To reduce early marriage and pregnancy.
 - 6) Trafficking of children.
- The rate of malnutrition in children from five years old maintains among the highest rate in the world.
 - The percentage of inequalities and impact on the urban and rural sector are drastically different, there is a huge gap between those sectors.

TO INVEST IN CHILDREN IS BETTER. Investing in children is not an expense, on the contrary is a commitment for the future.

INVESTIR MAIS É MELHOR NAS CRIANÇAS. Investir nas crianças não é uma despesa, mas uma aposta no futuro.

UNICEF Conference, Catholic University of Mozambique, Pemba
August 15, 2014.

The Situation of children in Mozambique in 2014, reflecting the voices of children.
Situação das crianças em Moçambique 2014. Refletindo as vozes das crianças.

DESCRIPTION OF INTERVENTION

General Objective

Games, jokes, music, theatre, tales, fables, imagination, landscape, friends, photos, images, body, tradition, culture and stories were all teaching tools to achieve the general goal: that of raising the children's motivation and enthusiasm for learning and communicating in Portuguese. Using with them a more interactive and communicative methodology than the traditional teacher-centred classes, making use of existing local resources, the children's imaginations and desire to learn.

Specific Objectives

To achieve the social and environmental inclusion of the children, so that they were able to interpret their reality, their environmental surroundings and its natural resources, its cultural richness and diversity.

- Encourage children to be sources of information in order to educate and motivate their parents and friends to speak Portuguese and to share information.
- Give the children the role of a communicator with society about the desire to be educated and able to educate in the future.
- Help give meaning and motivation to teachers in class about the importance of their role in modern society.
- Create trust, team working, friendship and cooperation between themselves and with the teachers.
- Work together with the Salesian Sisters in order to understand better the context, necessities, gain their support and involve them in the programme.

In achieving the above, I can reach the main purpose of this project: encouraging the use of Portuguese for communication and also helping the children to realise their potential.

I will also raise their awareness of why Mozambique is considered a country with rich and extensive natural wonders and resources which they have to look after as much as their own importance in their community and family.

Beneficiaries

There were multiple beneficiaries of this project. However, the most important of them were the children who attend the Salesian nurseries in Pemba. Their ages ranged from three years old to five years old.

Other beneficiaries were the local teachers, who were guided and taught the methodology used to teach the children.

The project was developed also with the support and guidance of the Salesian Sisters of Pemba.

The nurseries are maintained by the willingness and presence of the Salesian sisters and also two Catholic priests in this community.

From Monday to Friday these “Escolinhas” are supplied with food and water. A small truck brings food such as ground maize, corn, fruit, bread, fish, water and rice to feed about three hundred children daily.

The issue of malnutrition in Africa is widespread and in Mozambique it is a well-known and common reality. No one knows about tomorrow, but for day-to-day survival, the religious community finds a thousand ways to achieve the miracle of bringing food to the children despite their own domestic shortages.

Só precisamos de algumas cores, de pegar umas quantas folhinhas, se sentar pelo chão e, além disso, escutar uma boa historia para acabar a manhã de estúdio na escolinha.

WEEK BY WEEK

Each morning started with a 'warmer', usually Robot Gym (a physical activity to practice actions) and a welcome song. This was to indicate the beginning of the class and to make the students comfortable and happy to be there. This was followed by a review of the language from the day before to 'test' and help the memory of the children.

FIRST WEEK

IT WAS A LONG, HOT WALK

On that Monday morning, I walked on exotic roads for about three kilometres. I saw an endless sky, high valleys, and little villages. That is Africa, Mozambique, Pemba! The hills looked blue and far away.

The city was green and beautiful but at the same time there was a lot of rubbish everywhere. Women were walking along the road, they were dressed in beautiful 'capulanas' (traditional Mozambican skirts) some of them brightly coloured.

People were carrying heavy bundles on their heads. Children were playing, walking or carrying a baby on their backs.

Why weren't the children in school? I would like to know.

They are very inquisitive and they love foreigners staying in their community or just being able to chat to them for a while. A lot of people used to invite me to their homes, maybe in Italy or in Europe people don't do that.

**Escolinha Nossa Senhora da Esperança,
Natite**

When they saw the Salesian Sister Orsolina and me, they started shouting with excitement because we had arrived. The children had prepared a welcome song, which was incredible and unexpected.

I introduced myself to the whole group. Thankfully, I was working with 'Titias' (local teachers) because I don't speak Macua, one of the Mozambican languages, but luckily they always spoke Portuguese to me!

That first morning was exhausting but I knew it was worth it to see the smiles on their faces!

Finally, at about 8.30 a.m I arrived at the tiny school and it was already very hot. There were 70 kids sitting on the floor, just waiting for people to start learning, playing, singing, dancing, enjoying and smiling for the whole morning.

WEEK 2

ESCOLINHA DOM BOSCO DE CARIACO

After eating breakfast, the Salesian Sisters and Father Liberio told me to get ready. I put on some strong shoes and I filled my water bottle. I had learnt how to live in Pemba. That day, I didn't have to walk for several hours because I didn't know where the school was. Father Liberio drove a tiny truck, which was full of rice, bread, sugar, pasta, beans and water to supply the nursery. He does the same thing every single day!

Driving along the roads was like being on a roller coaster, up and down, during the journey we saw a huge landfill. It is called 'O lixeiro do bairro Cariaco' (the rubbish dump of the Cariaco neighbourhood). There was a lot of plastic, waste, food and a lot of little children were playing among the rubbish.

Questions, questions, questions were going around my head! What could they catch from there? It is frustrating and infuriating to see this.

Finally, I arrived at the nursery. I walked into the school where there were four classrooms and a lot of kids, 140 little cheeky monkeys running and playing. When they saw me, they ran up to me and tried to touch my long hair. They loved making braids in my hair!!!

I laughed and asked their names and then I started our lessons. Oh, it was very exciting! The kids were shouting and talking at the same time. My mind was more positively engaged. I was simply marvelling in the joy that their smiles brought to everyone around them.

It was a huge challenge, really!

WEEK 3

My third week in Africa and I am still learning a lot in Pemba. Life is exciting! I was going to walk around the Pemba outskirts and suburbs one more time. Doing this made me think about many things. Will it be dangerous? Will I get into trouble? And so on. Now I realised that I was just worried about safety and tropical diseases.

In fact, malaria was my main risk. The majority of Mozambicans catch it when they sleep; it is just a little fly that lives in the air and bites people. Consequently, the person starts to feel bad very slowly. In many villages, I saw kids and adults with malaria. Sometimes Mozambique is a difficult country: it's beautiful and interesting, but also dangerous. I understood that so I worked together with the community to take precautions.

ESCOLINHA SANTA TERESINHA DE LIOCE

At about 8 o'clock, I arrived in the Lioce neighbourhood. I walked down to the supermarket (African local grocery) and sat down on a rock. It was a long and hot walk! Just then, I saw a line of people. They were walking towards the village, some of them were kind to me and I greeted them by saying "hello and good morning" in Portuguese and sometimes in Macua.

There were a lot of tall trees beside the mud huts where the people in this neighbourhood live. They use bamboo to make the structure of the house. They then place it into the ground in a circular shape before putting mud and clay on it to reinforce it. Then, they let it dry and the walls are done. To do the roof they get bundles of hay and then they wrap it with something like string and arrange it for a roof.

At the nursery, I started to dance and sing to an African rhythm with the group. The children, their movements and that environment made me realise that it's important for African children to dance.

By the end of the week everything was fantastic! Enjoying the teaching, singing, painting, dancing and playing was a sure step to falling in love with Africa, with Mozambique, with Pemba!

Ernesto e Nelson, Os meninos mais espertos e carismáticos que eu tenha visto antes. A inteligência, a curiosidade e as ganhas de aprender podem se encontrar nestes anjinhos.

My teacher's pets, Ernesto and Nelson.

WEEK 4

WATER SHORTAGE

During this week I couldn't work.

To highlight the theme of nutrition, we explored the topic of breakfast. In Portuguese, breakfast is called 'Café da Manhã' in Brazil or 'small' Almoço in Portugal. In African countries, such as Angola and Mozambique, they use the expression 'Mata-bicho', which means simply "bug killer".

So, to have breakfast is 'mata-bichar' which literally translates as 'to kill the bug'. It comes from the concept that when someone wakes up in the morning feeling hungry, the wriggling feeling in your stomach is the 'bicho' (the bug). So, what better way to 'kill' it (soothe it) than with piece of bread or something!

To kill the bug, "Matabichar"

I really like this cute African-Portuguese expression. So, the children and Títias, 'kill the bug' every morning before learning, singing, jumping, dancing, laughing, playing, painting, running, listening to cartoons, and many more activities. It is very important to eat well in Pemba because the local conditions such as the weather, disease, illnesses and other things make it mandatory to have enough energy to carry on life normally.

As Títias preparando a "papinha" para matabichar juntas com as crianças antes de começar as aulas. A Panela fica sempre no fogão para aquecer e cozinhar.

Títias cooking "papinha" to have breakfast together with kids before starting lessons. A pot always stays on the fire to warm up and cook.

WEEK 5

ESCOLINHA LIOCE

My methodology for teaching Portuguese to the children was really focused on listening to music, singing and activities to improve their imagination. I also realised that I overestimated the children's capacity to remember and to imagine characters, roles, and to think in an abstract way.

In fact, this project was based on the concept of building their capacities, their imagination and a solid belief of creating spaces to play and learn before implementing other traditional methodologies of teaching. Following these objectives, it helped me to not feel frustrated with their progress. I know these kids have strengths and weaknesses during their educational process which are related to the culture, circumstances and resources.

*A doce menina Fada
A sweet little girl Fada*

Salpicos is a Mozambican dog who has got a family. The story describes how Salpicos from Monday to Friday tells us a new tale. The children were exposed to listening, vocabulary and we attempted to activate

their imaginations. We repeated parts of the story and all the characters and their roles in the family. Studies suggest that children between 4 and 12 years old need someone to read them a fable several times in order to retain words, situations, vocabulary and feelings. They also need to communicate their thoughts about the content of what they hear at the same time.

How exciting was our dog Salpicos!

Salpicos and his Mozambican family did a magnificent job in providing this resource, in other words the fable!

Every character and detail was correctly identified and a lot of time was taken by the children to obtain the highest understanding. Also, we were encouraging the local teachers 'Titias' to learn how to read and create a new story for the class.

We were completely sure that forcing students to remember something like a machine can interfere with their cognitive capacities during the beginning stages of school.

WEEK 6

VISITING ALL OF THE 'ESCOLINHAS' FOR THE LAST TIME

My last week in Pemba, Mozambique!

The desire to go back home was mixed with the feeling of a heavy weight inside me because I knew I had to say goodbye. I also felt a kind of ambition and hope that there is going to be a next time.

During that week, I had the opportunity to work with the three 'Escolinhas' and I divided up the days between them. To begin, I went to Natiti, then I spent two days in Cariaco, and finally one day in Lioce.

My activities focused on repeating and remembering all the activities that I did during the previous 5 weeks. I also had to emphasize the sustainability and continuity of the project in the future, because its success depends on the local teachers repeating and continuing my activities and timetables with the children

My methodology of using jokes, dancing, songs and games led to academic synergy which is very different from the methodology used by the local teachers. Teachers need to consider what it means to be a child and to learn how a child is at the centre of a good educational process. Using force does not give the child confidence or make them want to go to school. On the contrary, the child does not want to go to school and

learn and they become nervous, stressed and scared of what the teacher will do in retaliation. I made an extra effort to create an atmosphere where nothing was forced and I encouraged a policy of zero screaming or hitting. As much as possible, I communicated with the children and made them understand that they could enjoy learning and it did not matter if they made mistakes or failed. Most importantly they need to try and try again.

I did the activity of 'Tomatinho Vermelho' – The Little Red Tomato – which is a short story about how to prevent accidents in the streets. In Pemba, every day the traffic flow increases with the international companies that exploit natural resources in Mozambique, many tourists coming to have fun and western people arriving to develop economic activities.

The inhabitants of Pemba travel by rudimentary public transport without any precaution or awareness of pedestrians. They have no consciousness or thought to prevent injuring children who are used to playing in the street. This obviously results in very dangerous streets and it requires everyone to keep their eyes open and look from side to side before daring to cross the street or even just walking down the road. I knew it was a pretty sad story, 'Tomatinho' rolled and rolled down the

street, until a truck arrived and crushed him. He just wanted to play, but the only problem was that he forgot to be careful with the cars.

I told The Little Red Tomato's well-known story in the form of a play. I used a red balloon, which I decorated and painted like a tomato. During the course of the reading, the kids sat open-mouthed. They loved sitting and listening to the story. As I got to the end of the story, I exploded the balloon to represent what happened and some of the children started crying. They were very sad about what happened to The Little Red Tomato. I think the story made a big impact on them.

In addition, the theme of multiculturalism was present throughout my project. I created the Flag Game which involved making the Italian flag and Mozambique's flag. I wrote information about each country on the flags, such as the capitals, languages, customs, music and food. Then, we divided the whole group of children into two teams and we gave them an area where they practised running. We put a flag in each field to identify the Italians and the Mozambicans. The objective of the game was to create a third country with the two flags. The winning team was that who could unearth the opposing flag and place it next to theirs on their own ground.

All cultures are different, but the more we mix and share, the more we create a rich culture where our social capital generates spaces in which we enjoy and revitalize our cultural rights and also our traditions are materialized. In fact, there is no better experience for a foreigner or a native than to grab a chair and listen to someone talking about their traditions and customs, and also to show those into which he/she was born.

CONCLUSIONS

Taking all of this into account, I used many local resources such as the environment and situations experienced by the community day after day, their culture, traditions, and finally, in this way I put children as observers, in an analytical and participatory position by stimulating their abilities and potential according to their culture.

Result achieved, the children became more confident and trusting with me and also with the local teachers.

Result achieved, the children learnt a wide variety of Portuguese vocabulary, phrases and songs.

Result achieved, I raised the children's awareness of the importance of looking after the environment in which they live.

Result achieved, I raised the children's awareness of the importance of having a good level of personal hygiene.

SCHEDULE OF INTERVENTION

Week	Phase	Details
1	Introductory Phase: Building rapport, instilling confidence and gaining the trust of the children	Introduction phase of vocabulary (songs and educational games).
2	Phase 2 Raising awareness of issues with the environmental and hygiene	Education phase with environmental culture and society.
3	Phase 3 Creative part of children. Phase of interaction and fun	Production phase Developing abilities to speak and express thoughts Oral production.
4	Phase 4 Imaginative cultural interaction. The production of teaching materials in the classroom.	Developing abilities and retentive memory of children.
5	Phase 5 Music therapy, contact with nature and the school environment.	Strengthening vocabulary
6	Phase 6 Production of piece of work to bring back to Italy to show the results of the project	Building a friendship for life

RATIONALE OF METHODOLOGY

'Play opens the window of learning in a child's life and acquaints him or her with movement, observation, relationships, emotions and much more.'

As the title of the project suggests, the programme I designed had a strong emphasis on play and games. This is because research has proved that children who are active in play are normally more cheerful and cooperative, more willing to share and more creative. In addition, play can help children develop self-confidence, social skills such as concentration and cooperation; it allows them to relax, let off steam, encourages the development of the imagination and self-expression and develops motor skills.

Play provides the basis for learning in a child's world and opens a lot of doors for learning opportunities. In addition, I included a lot of songs and music as well as a stage of Music Therapy. Through music, children can connect with movement, rhythm and patterns. It can also help them to expand their imagination and helps to encourage physical fitness, balance and coordination. Also, music helps build social and emotional skills; it encourages children to use their own voice, to express their emotions, and work with others to create music. In fact, recent research additionally shows that it helps

develop children's memory and cognitive skills.

I also included a number of role-play activities. It is known that role-play can benefit children immensely. It helps them to understand the world around them, to learn about social interaction and to develop abstract thinking skills.

The other strong emphasis in the programme was on team building games. As I mentioned before, due to their difficult backgrounds, the children have little trust in other children and adults around them. I included a series of team games which were designed to motivate team working which in turn develop social skills, build trust and relationships and help the children feel more connected.

I truly believe that children need to feel comfortable and have the opportunities to express themselves as much as possible and I feel that this programme allowed them to do this.

RESULTS

USING FABLES TO TEACH LIFE LESSONS

Positive factors

Teachers, like many others who work with children, make use of fables when it comes to verbalising morals and teaching children valuable life lessons. Additionally, fables help promote good behaviour in a way that children become aware through the actions of characters in the narrative, in other words it comes from within the child. Fables also help children visualise what is invisible and describe what otherwise would be indescribable.

In Pemba, I used fables in Portuguese, with a lot of pictures and images to get my message across and help develop the children's imaginations. In the fables, I incorporated the role of the Mozambican family, their customs, traditions and a lot more which raised their awareness of a lot of issues such as social norms, good behaviour, personal hygiene, diversity and so on. The children really enjoyed the fables and I could see the positive effect they had on them and how it changed their way of thinking.

The fables also helped me to demonstrate a different methodology to teach children. In a system where the children are often punished, this is a way that the local teachers can teach them about and encourage good behaviour and the rewards it can bring. In addition, because, as I mentioned, the children love listening to these fables, the teachers were able to see that they can feel important and earn respect from the children. Also, the teachers realised that fables are an effective and powerful way to communicate very important messages.

Areas to think about

My biggest question is: after finishing this project, will local teachers continue to tell fables at the schools?

In terms of motivation, I do need to say that the teachers have a lot of economic problems which worry them. This is a big cause of the lack of motivation among the Mozambican teachers.

As I mentioned before, the local teachers did see the benefits of using fables but some of them told me that they did not have the creativity to invent new ones for the children. Because of this, I left the images of the characters from my fables and left written copies of

the fables I used. I also worked with them to invent one or two fables so that they learned how to do this themselves. However, bearing this in mind, it would be fantastic to provide the local teachers with a workshop on how to create fables to use with the children.

Topics

The following topics and activities were focused on in this project.

Cavities, brushing teeth, good manners, healthy diet, animals, fruits, sounds, dances, music, drawings, pictures, games, vocabulary

ISSUES WITH ACTIVITY DEVELOPMENT

Activities should always be sequenced from easy to difficult.

It was difficult to develop many of the activities into more challenging exercises due to the low level of concentration of the students and local teachers.

The teachers' attention must be ready to acquire the points being taught.

As I have already mentioned, due to reasons beyond my control, the teachers' motivation is not very high which led to a lack of retention of new activities.

Adapting classroom materials

Another issue which is beyond my control is the fact that there are very few resources and materials which means that there are limited types of activities I could do.

CONCLUSION

In Pemba, I did not have a manual to help me say the right things or to tell me how to deal with the children at the schools. However, I put all my effort into understanding their lives in their context, with their traditions and culture.

Most of all, I was, and still am, in absolute awe of the resilience of some of the young girls. They have to be strong, perhaps because their mothers are not there or because of the constant threat of sexual abuse against young Mozambican children.

I am also confident that did the best I could during this project to motivate and encourage these children to learn, to be better citizens and to hope for a brighter future.

I hope, one day, to return to Pemba and see these wonderful children again.

THANKS

Hips dance, black skin is revived, African blood flows. The sound of the drums is contagious and the sweet, unforgettable happy voices of the religious community still ring in my ears.

The church sounds and I feel the presence of our God. This is Africa, this is Mozambique, this is Pemba! Children sing and pray with devotion. It is a true religious spectacle to feel and participate in the community Mass.

Thank you for letting me take part in your religious community.

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